

URINARY DEDIFFERENTIATED PODOCYTES AS NON-INVASIVE BIOMARKER OF LUPUS NEPHRITIS

Running head: Dedifferentiated podocytes as biomarker of lupus nephritis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Currently, renal biopsy remains the gold standard for diagnosis and prognosis of lupus nephritis (LN). However, it is an invasive method and new non-invasive laboratory tests are needed to identify renal involvement without renal biopsy. Podocyte damage have an important role in the pathogenesis and progression of systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). We characterize whether the phenotype of urinary podocyte (viability, apoptosis, mRNA and protein levels of the podocyte-associated molecules) was a novel marker of clinical and histological features in SLE patients with or without LN.

Methods: We quantified in urinary sediments of 32 SLE patients and 20 controls, mRNA and protein levels of podocalyxin, synaptopodin, podocin, nephrin and WT-1 by qRT-PCR and Western blot analysis, and correlated with clinical and histological parameters. Viability of detached urine podocytes were analysed by flow cytometry with podocalyxin and annexin V/7-AAD double staining, and immunofluorescence of urine podocyte cultures.

Results: Apoptotic podocyte degree from urine samples was significant decreased in patients with LN, especially in active state (33 % compared to 75% in controls, $p < 0.001$), the majority of the detached podocytes into urine of patients with active LN were viable (70% grew in culture). Furthermore, urinary mRNA of podocyte associated molecules were significant lower in patients with active LN ($p < 0.05$) compared to healthy controls, and protein levels of podocyte markers were significantly increased in SLE patients, especially with LN compared to SLE without LN ($p < 0.05$) and healthy control group ($p < 0.01$). Finally, urinary protein levels of podocyte related markers were associated with proteinuria and histological features ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$), and ROC curves of protein levels discriminate between lupus

nephritis and healthy controls with an area under the curve (AUC) between 0.91 – 0.77 ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: Urinary dedifferentiated podocytes were showed in active lupus nephritis and their protein levels were correlated with proteinuria and histological features in LN. This preliminary results suggest it could be a potential useful non-invasive marker for evaluating progression of glomerular disease in SLE.

Keywords: Podocyte, mRNA, protein, lupus nephritis, systemic lupus erythematosus, urine.

SHORT SUMMARY

1. Urinary dedifferentiated podocytes were found into urine of patients with lupus nephritis
2. Low urinary mRNA expression and high urinary protein levels of podocyte associated protein levels were found in active lupus nephritis
3. Urinary protein levels were correlated with proteinuria and histological features in lupus nephritis, and had a statistical ROC curves for predicting lupus nephritis
4. Dedifferentiated podocytes in urine could be a potential useful non-invasive marker for evaluating progression of glomerular disease in SLE, and considering urine as a liquid biopsy.

BACKGROUND

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic autoimmune disease with multiple organ involvement affecting mostly women [1]. Lupus nephritis (LN) is recognized as one of the most severe organ manifestation of SLE [2]. Depending on the severity of disease, 10–30% of these patients will progress to end-stage renal disease [3]. Clinical manifestations of active LN include proteinuria, active urinary sediments, and progressive renal dysfunction [4]. The pathogenesis of LN is a complex process, involving deposition of autoantibodies in the glomerulus, activation of complement and macrophages, production of pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines [5,6]. However, the exact pathogenesis of LN is incompletely understood [7,8].

Recent insights have defined the role of podocytes in the pathogenesis of glomerulosclerosis [9], being a urinary marker of glomerular disease [10-12]. Moreover, analysis of podocyte-associated molecules in kidney tissue or in urinary sediment has emerged as a valuable non-invasive method for studying and monitoring kidney diseases [13-17]. In fact, mRNA expression of podocyte-associated molecules, such as nephrin, podocin and synaptopodin have been quantified in patients with diabetic nephropathy [18], and mRNA levels of cytokines for the prediction of flare in SLE [19].

Studies analysing simultaneously different podocyte-derived biomarkers to identify the phenotype of detached podocytes in urinary sediment in SLE with or without glomerular disease have not been performed. Therefore, we characterized the phenotype of urinary podocytes, as viability and apoptosis degree, mRNA and protein levels of the podocyte-associated molecules for apical membrane (podocalyxin), slit diaphragm (nephrin and podocin), actin-based cell shape

(synaptopodin) and transcription factor WT-1, in SLE patients with or without lupus nephritis (LN). In addition, we examined whether they were associated with clinical and histological parameters.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Human subjects: patients and healthy controls

Thirty-two patients with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) (4 men and 28 women; mean aged 42.5 years) and 20 healthy controls (4 men and 16 women; mean aged 35.3 years) in the absence of SLE and normal renal function, were included in this study. All the SLE patients satisfied the American College of Rheumatology classification criteria for SLE [2] and the disease activity of SLE was assessed clinically by an independent physician with the Systemic Lupus Erythematosus Disease Activity Index (SLEDAI) [20]. The presence of active lupus nephritis (LN) (active LN, n=10) were considered with impaired kidney function with proteinuria (>0.5 g/24 h or >1 g/24 h with previous proteinuria) or an active urine sediment, that includes haematuria, especially leukocyturia in the absence of infection, and red and white blood cell casts, or kidney biopsy with active glomerulonephritis. Remission LN (n=10) was considered when the patients decreased the proteinuria levels (< 0.5 g/24h) and had remission urinary sediment with stable kidney function. In addition, twelve SLE in absence of LN (disease-control group) were also studied. Baseline serum creatinine, 24-hour proteinuria, complement levels (C3 and C4) and anti-double strand (ds) DNA antibody were measured. Glomerular filtration rate (GFR) was estimated by MDRD formula. Categories of LN renal biopsy were based on classification by the International Society of Nephrology and Renal Pathology Society (ISN/RPS) [21]. Written informed consent was obtained from all the participating

subjects. All the study protocols and consent forms were approved by the Ethics Committee of the *Hospital Clinico Universitario of Valencia*, which abides by the Helsinki Declaration on ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. A whole-stream first morning urine specimen of each subject (200 mL) was collected in sterile containers and were processed within 1 h after collection.

Podocytic apoptosis detected by flow cytometry

After collection of first-morning urine, two 30 mL of urine were separately transferred into two sterile falcon tubes, and were centrifuged 5 min at 400 g. Sediments were washed with sterile PBS and centrifuged 5 min at 400 g once again. The first tube was then incubated with 15 μ L allophycocyanin (APC)-conjugated mouse monoclonal anti-human podocalyxin (R&D Systems) and the second tube was incubated with 15 μ L allophycocyanin (APC)-conjugated mouse IgG_{2A} isotype control antibody (R&D Systems) for 30 min at room temperature in the dark. After the incubation, the sediments were washed and resuspended in 500 μ L of 1 mL binding buffer (Annexin V Binding Buffer, Immunostep, Spain). Double Annexin V/7-AAD staining was applied for 15 min at room temperature in the dark following manufacturer's instructions (Immunostep, Spain). For the assay, 35,000 cells were analysed by flow cytometer (FACSverse) with FACSuite software (BD, Bioscience, USA).

These results were confirmed by the culture of urinary sediments from patients and healthy controls and immunofluorescence analysis of podocalyxin and synaptopodin in the primary urinary cells that grown on 24-well-dishes (experimental details in supporting information).

Homogenization of samples, electrophoresis and Western blot analysis

Urinary cell pellets from 50 mL first morning urine were lysed in RIPA lysis buffer with protease inhibitor cocktail (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO), and protein concentration

was determined by Lowry method using bovine serum albumin (BSA) as standard. Total cell lysate (equal to 20 µg of protein) were separated by NuPAGE 4–12% Bis-Tris polyacrylamide gels (Invitrogen Ltd, UK). Following electrophoresis, gels were transferred to PVDF membranes for western blotting. After blocking all night with 1% BSA, membranes were incubated for 2 hours with a primary antibody: mouse monoclonal anti-synaptopodin antibody (Progen Biotechnik, Germany), mouse monoclonal nephrin (Acris, Germany), rabbit polyclonal WT-1 (Abcam, England), rabbit polyclonal aquaporin-1 (Millipore, USA) and mouse monoclonal podocalyxin antibody and rabbit polyclonal podocin (Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Germany). Anti- β -actin monoclonal antibody (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) was used as loading control. Then, the bands were visualized using an acid phosphatase-conjugated secondary antibody (NBT/BCIP, Sigma) substrate system. Finally, the bands were digitalized using an image analyser (DNR Bio-Imaging Systems) and quantified by the TotalLab TL-100 (v.2008) program.

RNA Extraction and Reverse Transcription

A 50 mL aliquot of first morning urine were centrifuged 30 min at 2,250g in order to pellet urine cells. Total RNA was extracted from urinary pellets using the miRNeasy mini kit (reference 217004, Qiagen, CA) following manufacturer's protocol. All extractions were immediately after urine collection. The RNA was eluted in 50 µL and stored at -80°C until used. Total RNA concentration and purity was confirmed by an $A_{260/280}$ absorbance ratio, using NanoDrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Technologies, DE). A fixed amount of 300 ng RNA were reverse transcribed to cDNA using the Ready-To-Go You-Prime First-Strand Beads (GE Healthcare Bio-sciences, NJ, US)..

Real-Time Quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction

A volume of 2 μ L of cDNA was used to perform the real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using a 480 II real-time PCR system (Roche). All reactions were run in triplicate, including blank/negative controls without cDNA. Corresponding primers are shown in Supplementary Table S1. Data was analysed with the apparatus software (v1.5), determining the threshold cycle (Ct) and the average of each sample. The amount of mRNA from two housekeeping genes, β -actin and β -2-microglobulin, was used to normalize podocyte-specific gene expression and the specificity of the product was controlled by melting curve analysis. In order to calculate the differences of expression level for each target gene among samples, the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ comparative method for relative quantitation was used.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were performed with Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (v 12.1.3 for Windows; IBM SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Mann-Whitney U-test and Fisher's exact test were used to determine the difference of clinical characteristics between two groups where appropriate. The mRNA data was presented as the median fold change relative to control group and protein levels were expressed as the median (interquartile range). The nonparametric Mann-Whitney U-test was used to compare differences in apoptotic degree, relative fold changes of mRNAs and protein levels between disease groups. Relationships between mRNA and protein levels with clinical parameters were compared using Spearman correlation coefficient test. We constructed ROC curves and calculated the area under the ROC curve (AUC) to identify their associations with SLE and lupus nephritis. A P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Study population. The baseline clinical data of the study subjects are summarized in Table 1. Of the 32 SLE patients: ten had active lupus nephritis (proteinuria 1.98 ± 0.58 g/24 h), ten had remission lupus nephritis (0.44 ± 0.21 g /24 h) and twelve had SLE in absence of lupus nephritis (disease-control group) (0.12 ± 0.08 g/day). Active LN group had worse renal function with higher proteinuria and GFR than controls ($p < 0.01$), remission LN and in the absence of LN ($p < 0.05$). Baseline serum C3 and C4 levels were also significantly lower in active LN patients compared to remission LN ($p < 0.05$).

Podocytic apoptosis in urinary sediment of patients with lupus nephritis. An increase in PDX positive cells in patients with LN compared to controls were observed, 3-fold increase in active state and 2-fold increase in remission LN (Figure 1). In addition, analysing only in PDX-positive cell group, the podocytic apoptosis rates were significantly lower in urine samples from both LN, active and remission (Figure 1B and 1C), especially in patients with active LN compared to controls (33.4% vs 75%, $p < 0.001$) or than remission LN group (56.8%, $p < 0.01$). Flow cytometry showed that most of the podocytes in the urine of patients with active LN were not apoptotic, but not in healthy controls (Figure 1A, 1C). Sixty-four percent of PDX-positive cells in patients with active LN and 23% in controls would be viable podocytes (Figure 1D). These results were confirmed by the culture growth of viable podocytes in the 80% of urine specimens from patients with active lupus nephritis, and only 10% of healthy controls (supplementary Figure S1).

mRNA levels of podocyte associated proteins in urinary sediment. The expression levels of podocalyxin, nephrin, podocin, synaptopodin, WT-1 and AQ1 are summarized in Figure 2. Urinary mRNA expressions of the studied targets were significantly lower in patients with active LN than in healthy controls (4.3-fold

decrease for WT-1 and 4.4-fold decrease for synaptopodin, $p < 0.01$; and 3.6-fold decrease for nephrin, 3.3-fold decrease for podocin, $p < 0.05$) and not differences were observed in mRNA between patients with remission or SLE patients without LN with healthy controls. However, mRNA levels of podocalyxin were significantly increased in active LN compared to controls (2.3-fold change, $p < 0.01$) and in patients with remission lupus nephritis (1.9-fold change, $p < 0.01$). Similar aquaporin-1 mRNA values were obtained between groups.

Protein levels of podocyte-associated proteins in urinary sediment. Protein levels of podocalyxin, synaptopodin, podocin, nephrin, WT-1 and aquaporin1 were shown in Figure 3. All molecules were significantly increased in active LN group compared to healthy subjects (7.2-fold increase for podocalyxin, 6.8-fold increase for synaptopodin, 6.7-fold increase for podocin, 4.6-fold increase for nephrin, with $p < 0.01$; and 2.9-fold increase for WT-1 and 2.3-fold increase for aquaporin-1, with $p < 0.05$). Patients with remission LN also had a smaller increase in protein levels of molecules studied than controls ($p < 0.05$), with the exception of aquaporin-1. In addition, there were significant differences between active LN and SLE without glomerular disease (disease control group) ($p < 0.01$ for podocalyxin, synaptopodin and nephrin, and $p < 0.05$ for podocin and WT-1) (Figure 3).

Association with clinical variables and histological features in patients with lupus nephritis. The mRNA levels of synaptopodin, nephrin and WT-1 were inversely correlated with proteinuria levels ($p < 0.05$), but only podocalyxin showed a direct correlation with proteinuria ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2). In addition, protein levels of all associated-podocyte molecules studied were significantly related with proteinuria, overall podocalyxin and synaptopodin ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$, respectively), and were not correlated with GFR values (Table 3). On the other hand, we have analysed the

association between protein and mRNA values with the ISN/RPS 2003 classification of LN in ten renal biopsies (Figure 4). We found significant increase of median urinary proteins with the histological features (Type II+III versus Type IV+V) ($p < 0.01$): podocalyxin [162 (124-269) versus 874 (423-1195)], synaptopodin [124 (84-253) versus 429 (358-888)], podocin [217 (99-277) versus 696 (493-1051)], nephrin [111 (100-210) versus 412 (353-798)] and WT-1 [199 (64-204) versus 425 (308-509)]. Whereas mRNA levels did not reach statistical differences (Supplementary Fig S1).

ROC-curve analysis of mRNA and protein levels of podocyte-associated

molecules. ROC curves were calculated to assess the power for mRNA and protein levels of podocyte molecules in discriminating between SLE patients with lupus nephritis (active and remission) and controls (Table 4). Protein levels of podocalyxin, synaptopodin, podocin, nephrin and WT-1 showed significant AUC ($p < 0.01$), but only podocalyxin mRNA values had significant AUC. In addition, protein levels of these molecules were able to discriminate between SLE patients with ($n=20$) or without lupus nephritis (disease-control group, $n=12$), with AUC >0.77 . The highest value of AUC was 0.91 (95% CI, 0.82–0.99, $p < 0.001$) for podocalyxin protein levels. Only podocalyxin mRNA levels showed an AUC of 0.49 (95% CI 0.25-0.79, $p < 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

In the present study, urinary mRNA and protein levels of podocyte-derived molecules were simultaneously quantified together with the podocyte apoptosis to characterize the phenotype of podocytes shed into urine of patients with SLE. The phenotype of the podocytes isolated from urine and the podocyte-derived mRNA and protein levels differed in the presence of LN as compared to SLE without nephritis (disease-control

group) and controls. In active LN, the majority of podocytes shed into urine showed a phenotype associated with reduced urinary mRNA levels of podocyte-associated molecules, increased protein levels and decreased apoptotic rate. The preliminary observed cellular and molecular pattern would point to that the detachment of podocytes could mainly due to a de-differentiation process in the active LN stage. Moreover, urinary mRNA and especially urinary protein levels of dedifferentiated podocyte were significantly related with clinical and histological features in LN, considering urine as a potential liquid biopsy in these patients.

Podocyte injury and loss play a direct role in the pathogenesis and progression of glomerulosclerosis [22- 24]. When injured, podocytes undergo histologically notable changes in structure, termed effacement, where the normal cellular architecture of the foot process is altered and results in flattening and spreading of the foot process and disruption of the slit diaphragm. Persistent podocyte injury produces irreversible changes (hypertrophy, metabolic networks disruption, autophagy ...) that lead to cell death, senescence, apoptosis and detachment of podocytes into urine, causing progressive and severe glomerular damage [25,26]. Therefore, the determination of urinary podocyte loss become a non-invasive tool in the evaluation of glomerular diseases. We have performed flow cytometer experiments with podocalyxin and AnnexinV/7-AAD double staining and we observed that was an increase of PDX-positive cells in patients with lupus nephritis compared to controls (3-fold change in active state and 2-fold change in remission). Furthermore, the percentage of apoptotic podocalyxin positive cells were decreased in patients with LN, especially in the active disease. In urine sediments of 80% of patients and 10% of healthy controls grew podocytes in culture. Results confirmed by immunofluorescence staining for podocalyxin and synaptopodin.

As described above, the fact that the majority of podocytes shed into urine in active LN are viable, suggest that they are excreted into urine not as a result of apoptosis but as a result of other mechanisms due to local environmental factors, that lead to the podocyte de-differentiation [27], losing the specialized features. Thus, urinary podocytes would not maintain differentiated phenotype and not need to express molecules associated to basal or slit diaphragm regions of podocytes such as podocin, synaptopodin or nephrin. This fact is in concordance with the significant decrease in urinary mRNA levels of podocyte-associated molecules in SLE with renal injury (LN), with the exception of podocalyxin that was augmented, perhaps because glomerular podocytes are highly polarized cells and this protein is localized in apical membrane on the pathological events present in active LN affects differently [28,29]. Furthermore, our results showed that aquaporin-1 mRNA levels (a marker of proximal tubule function) were similar in patients and controls, and were not correlated with clinical variables. These findings supported the specificity of glomerular changes (podocyte alterations) in patients with lupus nephritis.

Previous works have found that in response to TGF- β , mature podocytes undergo dedifferentiation that leads to “pathoadaptive” changes such as a decrease in the expression of key genes of podocytes, contributing to podocytopenia and the consequent increase in protein filtration [30]. Sato et al. showed that detached podocytes lose their nephrin expression at the mRNA level during the progression phase of glomerular injury [31]. However, urinary mRNA expressions of nephrin, podocin, synaptopodin, WT-1 and α -actinin-4 were reported higher in patients with diabetic nephropathy [18], and the degree of up-regulation have linked to progression of glomerular diseases including diabetes and SLE [19, 32, 33].

The protein levels of podocyte-associated molecules studied in urinary sediment, showing augmented values of podocalyxin, podocin, nephrin, synaptopodin and WT-1 protein levels, with the highest increase in patients with active LN. Despite the lower expression mRNA levels of basal and slit diaphragm proteins, the high number of podocytes (apoptotic or viable) shed to urine increases the protein levels of these molecules detected in urine. Furthermore, fragments of podocytes have also been demonstrated in human urine [27].

Finally, significant correlations were observed between protein level of podocyte-associated molecules and degree of proteinuria in patients with lupus nephritis whereas mRNA levels of podocalyxin, synaptopodin, nephrin and WT-1 showed an inverse correlation with proteinuria. This fact could be explained because urinary podocytes of patients with active lupus nephritis had a lower mRNA expression of these molecules. However, a significant increase in urinary protein levels of associated-podocyte proteins with the gravity of histological features were obtained. Finally, ROC curve analysis revealed a good discriminatory role of urinary protein levels of podocyte-expressed molecules for LN, whereas mRNA did not reach significant AUC, except to mRNA expression of podocalyxin. These preliminary results suggest an association between phenotype of podocytes shed into urine with the progression of SLE.

There were some limitations in this study. First, the relative small sample of patients included, studies involving a larger patient cohort are needed for further confirmation of results. Secondly, control and patient groups were not matched for age, but we did not find significant correlations between this clinical variable with mRNA and protein levels of podocyte-associated molecules. Thirdly, we cannot rule out exposition to extreme conditions in the final urine that could induce podocyte

undergo apoptosis. However, this fact would affect all samples equally and our SLE groups showed different mRNA and protein profiles. Furthermore, the similar mRNA levels of aquaporin-1, a kidney-specific gene robustly expressed and a marker of proximal tubule function, pointed to a specific decrease in mRNA podocyte-associated molecules. Finally, an enrichment of podocytes in urine sediment could be of interest to avoid confounding results by different cell types present in urine, but the molecules analysed were specific markers of podocytes.

In conclusion, our investigation suggest a dedifferentiated phenotype of podocytes in urinary sediment in patients with lupus nephritis, and the protein levels of molecules associated to these dedifferentiated podocytes could be used as non-invasive marker in the progression of glomerular disease in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. Further studies with larger numbers of patients are warranted in order to confirm our preliminary results and to identify the specific mechanisms of loss of viable podocytes.

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Conflict of interest

All authors report no conflict of interest. All authors declaring that the results presented in this paper have not been published previously in whole or part, except in abstract format.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Rahman A, Isenberg DA. Systemic lupus erythematosus. *N Engl J Med* 2008; 358: 929–939.
2. Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) Glomerulonephritis Work Group. KDIGO Clinical Practice Guideline for Glomerulonephritis. *Kidney Inter Suppl* 2012; 2:139–274.
3. Ortega LM, Schultz DR, Lenz O, Pardo V, Contreras GN. Review: Lupus nephritis: pathologic features, epidemiology and a guide to therapeutic decisions. *Lupus* 2010;19:557–74.
4. Hill GS, Delahousse M, Nochy D, Mandet C, Bariéty J. Proteinuria and tubulointerstitial lesions in lupus nephritis. *Kidney Int* 2001;60:1893-903.
5. Tang S, Lui SL, Lai KN. Pathogenesis of lupus nephritis: an update. *Nephrology (Carlton)* 2005;10:174-9.
6. Gigante A, Gasperini ML, Afeltra A, et al. Cytokines expression in SLE nephritis. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci* 2011;15:15–24.
7. Rekvig OP, Van der Vlag J. The pathogenesis and diagnosis of systemic lupus erythematosus: still not resolved. *Semin Immunopathol* 2014;36:301-11.
8. Frangou EA, Bertsias GK, Boumpas DT. Gene expression and regulation in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Eur J Clin Invest* 2013;43:1084-96
9. Wiggins RC. The spectrum of podocytopathies: A unifying view of glomerular disease. *Kidney Int* 2007;71:1205-14.
10. Nakamura T, Ushiyama C, Suzuki S, et al. Urinary podocytes for the assessment of disease activity in lupus nephritis. *Am J Med Sci* 2000;320:112-6.

11. Vogelmann SU, Nelson WJ, Myers BD, Lemley KV. Urinary excretion of viable podocytes in health and renal disease. *Am J Physiol Renal Physiol* 2003;285:F40-8.
12. Sun D, Zhao X, Meng L. Relationship between urinary podocytes and kidney diseases. *Ren Fail* 2012;34:403-7.
13. Koop K, Eikmans M, Baelde HJ, et al. Expression of podocyte-associated molecules in acquired human kidney diseases. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2003;14:2063-71.
14. Perysinaki GS, Moysiadis DK, Bertias G, et al. Podocyte main slit diaphragm proteins, nephrin and podocin, are affected at early stages of lupus nephritis and correlate with disease histology. *Lupus* 2011;20:781-91.
15. Zheng M, Lv LL, Ni J, et al. Urinary podocyte-associated mRNA profile in various stages of diabetic nephropathy. *PLoS One* 2011;6:e20431.
16. Guan J, Wang G, Tam LS, et al. Urinary sediment ICAM-1 level in lupus nephritis. *Lupus* 2012;21:1190-5.
17. Szeto CC, Kwan BC, Tam LS. Urinary mRNA in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Adv Clin Chem* 2013;62:197-219.
18. Wang G, Lai FM, Lai KB, Chow KM, Li KT, Szeto CC. Messenger RNA expression of podocyte-associated molecules in the urinary sediment of patients with diabetic nephropathy. *Nephron Clin Pract* 2007;106:c169-79.
19. Szeto CC, Tam LS, Kwan BC, et al. Monitoring of urinary messenger RNA levels for the prediction of flare in systemic lupus erythematosus. *Clin Chim Acta* 2012;413:448-55.
20. Urowitz MB, Gladman DD. Measures of disease activity and damage in SLE. *Clin Rheumatol* 1998;12:405-13.

21. Markowitz GS, D'Agati VD. The ISN/RPS 2003 classification of lupus nephritis: an assessment at 3 years. *Kidney Int* 2007;71:491-5.
22. Kim YH, Goyal M, Kurnit DM, et al. Podocyte depletion and glomerulosclerosis have a direct relationship in the PAN-treated rat. *Kidney Int* 2001;60:957-68.
23. Lemley KV, Lafayette RA, Safai M, et al. Podocytopenia and disease severity in IgA nephropathy. *Kidney Int* 2002;61:1475-85.
24. Wharram BL, Goyal M, Wiggins JE, et al. Podocyte depletion causes glomerulosclerosis: Diphtheria toxin-induced podocyte depletion in rats expressing human diphtheria toxin receptor transgene. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2005;16:2941-52.
25. Greka A, Mundel P. Cell biology and pathology of podocytes. *Annu Rev Physiol* 2012;74:299-323.
26. Mundel P, Shankland SJ. Podocyte biology and response to injury. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2002;13:3005-15.
27. May CJ, Saleem M, Welsh GI. Podocyte dedifferentiation: a specialized process for a specialized cell. *Front Endocrinol (Lausanne)* 2014;5:148.
28. Hara M, Yanagihara T, Kihara I, Higashi K, Fujimoto K, Kajita T. Apical cell membranes are shed into urine from injured podocytes: a novel phenomenon of podocyte injury. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2005;16:408-16.
29. Hara M, Yamagata K, Tomino Y, et al. Urinary podocalyxin is an early marker for podocyte injury in patients with diabetes: establishment of a highly sensitive ELISA to detect urinary podocalyxin. *Diabetologia* 2012;55:2913-9.
30. Herman-Edelstein M, Thomas MC, Thallas-Bonke V, Saleem M, Cooper ME, Kantharidis P. Dedifferentiation of immortalized human podocytes in response

to transforming growth factor- β : a model for diabetic podocytopathy. *Diabetes* 2011;60:1779-88.

31. Sato Y, Wharram BL, Lee SK, et al. Urine podocyte mRNAs mark progression of renal disease. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2009;20:1041-52.

32. Wang G, Lai FM, Lai KB, et al. Urinary messenger RNA expression of podocyte-associated molecules in patients with diabetic nephropathy treated by angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor and angiotensin receptor blocker. *Eur J Endocrinol* 2008;158:317–22.

33. Wang G, Lai FM, Tam LS, et al. Messenger RNA expression of podocyte-associated molecules in urinary sediment of patients with lupus nephritis. *J Rheumatol* 2007;34:2358-64.

Table 1. Baseline clinical data of the study subjects

Characteristic	SLE (n=32)	Healthy Controls (n=20)
Age	42.53± 9.8*	35.26 ± 7.06
Gender (Male/Female)	4/28	4/16
Serum creatinine (mg/dL)	0.88 ± 0.41	0.72 ± 0.12
GFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	89.70 ± 13.41	104.48 ± 13.79
Proteinuria (g/24 h)	0.67 ± 0.65	n.d.
Anti-dsDNA (UI/mL)	152.89 ± 21.05	n.d.
C3 (mg/dL)	61.17 ± 3.2	n.d.
C4 (mg/dL)	13.96 ± 8.10	n.d.
SLEDAI	8.15 ± 5.47	n.d.

The data are expressed as the mean ± SD, unless noted otherwise.

Anti-dsDNA: Anti-double-stranded DNA; C3: complement 3, C4: complement 4; GFR: glomerular filtration rate; LN: lupus nephritis; n.d.: non determined; SLE: systemic lupus erythematosus; SLEDAI: SLE activity index. *p < 0.05 compared to controls.

Table 2. Associations between mRNA levels of podocyte-associated molecules in urinary sediment with proteinuria and estimated glomerular filtration rate in lupus nephritis patients.

mRNA Levels	Proteinuria (g/day)	GFR (mL/min/1.73 m²)
Podocalyxin	0.336*	-0.256
Synaptopodin	-0.354*	-0.190
Podocin	-0.290	-0.138
Nephrin	-0.394*	-0.262
WT-1	-0.528*	-0.217
Aquaporin1	0.125	-0.230

Data correlated by Spearman's correlation coefficient. GFR: glomerular filtration rate.

* p < 0.05

Table 3. Relations between protein levels of podocyte-associated molecules in urinary sediment with proteinuria and estimated glomerular filtration rate in lupus nephritis patients.

Protein Levels	Proteinuria (g/day)	GFR (mL/min/1.73 m²)
Podocalyxin	0.634*	-0.106
Synaptopodin	0.812**	-0.204
Podocin	0.167	-0.127
Nephrin	0.430*	-0.314
WT-1	0.614*	-0.240
Aquaporin1	0.121	-0.284

Data compared by Spearman's correlation coefficient. * p < 0.05; ** p < 0.001. GFR: glomerular filtration rate.

Table 4. ROC curve analysis of mRNA and protein levels of podocyte-associated molecules between patients with lupus nephritis and controls.

		AUC (95% CI)	P value
Podocalyxin	mRNA	0.49 (0.25-0.79)	0.029
	Protein	0.91 (0.82-0.99)	0.0001
Podocin	mRNA	0.37 (0.17-0.56)	0.325
	Protein	0.77 (0.66-0.95)	0.001
Synaptopodin	mRNA	0.37 (0.27-0.81)	0.321
	protein	0.90 (0.79-0.99)	0.0001
Nephrin	mRNA	0.37 (0.12-0.63)	0.254
	protein	0.86 (0.73-0.97)	0.0001
WT-1	mRNA	0.30 (0.12-0.69)	0.225
	protein	0.79 (0.63-0.94)	0.005

ROC curves discriminating patients with lupus nephritis (n=16) and controls (n=15).

AUC, area under the curve; CI, confidence interval.

FIGURE LEGENDS

Figure 1. Podocyte apoptosis in urinary sediment of patients with lupus nephritis. Podocyte cell death was determined by Podocalyxin (PDX) and AnnexinV/7-AAD double staining followed by flow cytometry in (A) controls, (B) remission LN and (C) active LN. (D) Quantitative analysis by: Black bar represents the mean percentage of cells \pm SEM of PDX/annexin V positive/PI-negative (apoptotic) cells, and white bar represent PDX/annexin V negative/PI-negative (viable) cells in the SLE groups with lupus nephritis and controls. For the assay, 35,000 total cells were analysed by sample (n = 3 each group) for quantified apoptosis only in PDX positive cells. ** p < 0.01 compared to controls. *** p < 0.001 compared to controls. # p < 0.05 compared to active lupus nephritis.

Figure 2. Comparison of mRNA levels of podocyte associated proteins in urinary sediment between systemic lupus erythematosus groups and healthy controls. Boxes display median (horizontal bars), interquartile ranges (lower and upper limits of boxes), and 5th and 95th percentiles (error bars). CNT, controls; LN, lupus nephritis; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus without lupus nephritis. Data compared by Mann-Whitney U-test. Relative expression were shown which was calculated with the equation $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$, relative to the control average. * p < 0.05 compared to controls; ** p < 0.01 compared to controls.

Figure 3. Comparison of protein levels of podocyte associated proteins in urinary sediment between systemic lupus erythematosus groups and healthy controls quantify. Boxes display median (horizontal bars), interquartile ranges (lower and upper limits of boxes), and 5th and 95th percentiles (error bars). CNT, controls; LN, lupus nephritis; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus without lupus nephritis. Data compared by Mann-Whitney U-test. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM of five

independent experiments and normalized to β -actin and finally to CNT samples, which was also normalized to β -actin before. * $p < 0.05$ compared to healthy controls; ** $p < 0.01$ compared to healthy controls. # compared to SLE disease-control groups.

Figure 4. Protein levels of molecules associated of podocytes with the severity of histological features according to ISN/RPS 2003 classification. Lupus nephritis (LN) Class II + III (n=5) and Class IV + V (n=5). Significant differences were observed. ** $p < 0.01$.

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